

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT TRANSPLANTING DATES AND HYBRIDS ON ECONOMICS OF TOMATO (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) GROWN UNDER POLYHOUSE CONDITIONSDiksha Saini¹, Amit Saurabh^{*2}, Ruksana³, Vedika Sharma⁴, Himanshi⁵ and Pallvi Sharma⁶

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Abstract

The recent research project took place at the Experimental Research Farm Chhapang of the Dr. Khem Singh Gill Akal College of Agriculture, Eternal University, Baru Sahib, district of Sirmour, Himachal Pradesh to know and understand more about the effect of different transplanting dates and hybrids on economics of tomatoes throughout the months of March-September, 2022. By employing three alternative transplanting dates and three hybrids that were replicated three times, the experimental trial was set up in a Randomized Block Design. By weighing benefit versus cost, tomato production is lucrative. The current study's findings showed that higher gross return (418.69 Rs./m²), net return (195.64 Rs./m²) and benefit cost ratio (0.88) all were recorded in interaction H₃D₂ (TO-1057 which was transplanted on 15th April), which is due to production of good quality fruits along with better yield, which has resulted in selling of tomato fruits at higher rate. Hence, from the present study we could recommend that farmers should grow TO-1057 on April 15, in order to achieve higher profit or benefit.

Keywords: Benefit, Cost, Economics, Quality, Transplanting dates, Yield

Introduction

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is the one of the most delicate crop, whose market price varies wildly from year to year. The word "tomato" is a widespread name used throughout the world that comes from the Spanish usage of the Náhuatl word "xictomatli" (xictli: navel and tomatil: tomato) from Mexico, which means the tomato with a navel. This is referring to the peduncle-induced scar on the fruit. The plant is usually referred to as "jitomate" in Mexico (OECD iLibrary, 2017). The tomato fruits are described as berries, the size and weight of which vary with the varieties. Its fruit, leaf and vine are sometimes used as to make medicine. Another name for a tomato is "poor man's orange" (Marasini and Paudel, 2017).

India, the world's top exporter of tomatoes, sends the majority of them to the Maldives, the United Arab Emirates, and the United States. India, Turkey, and Italy are the top 3 exporters of tomatoes, accounting for 133,908 shipments, 129,327 shipments, and 122,520 shipments, respectively (Volza Grow Global, 2022). Asia's largest tomato market, Madanapalle, in the Chittoor district, covers more than 20,000 farmers and more than one lakh hectares, and it generates a yearly turnover of several hundred crores of rupees (thehindu.com, 2022). 100 million tonnes of fresh fruit are produced globally now from 3.7 million ha. (FAO, 2022). Presently India production is about 20.3 Million tonnes of fresh fruit from 8.31 Lakh ha. area. (The Ministry of Agriculture and Farmer Welfare, 2021-2022). Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Odisha and Gujarat are major tomato producing states in India.

Thus, the tomatoes grown in greenhouses have many benefits over those grown in open field conditions, the yield per acre in greenhouses can be up to 15 times higher than in open field conditions. Time of transplanting is an important component that results in development of proper growth of plants that leads to maximum yield, better quality and higher benefit cost ratio. So, the desirable hybrid transplanted at suitable time which results in higher yield, better quality which results higher benefit cost ratio. It shall be recommended for cultivation under protected conditions.

Material and Methods

The experimental research was carried out during the months of summer (March-September, 2022) in a polyhouse with natural ventilation in Himachal Pradesh, at Experimental Research Station Chhapang, Dr. Khem Singh Gill Akal College of Agriculture, Eternal University, Baru Sahib, District Sirmour. The evaluation area of experimental site was 898 metres high from mean sea level at a latitude of 30.73° north and a longitude of 77.31° east. The experimental area experiences the coldest weather in December and

January and the hottest weather in May and June whereas the temperature ranges 15° to 36° C with relative humidity of 80% due to presence of subtropical condition in particular area of experiment. The research trail was set by using Randomized Block Design with treatments were replicated three times. The three different dates of transplanting with 15 days intervals (30th March, 15th April, 30th April) and three different hybrids (Heem Shona, Abhinav and TO-1057). The entire plot was laid out in three blocks, each having nine plots measuring 2 m × 1.5 m, for a total of 27 unit plots. The drain was maintained at a distance of 0.5 m between plots and 1.0 m between blocks. Rows and plants were isolated by 60 cm between them and 45 cm between them, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Economics of tomato production under polyhouse conditions along with different hybrids and different transplanting dates were responded significantly toward for benefit cost ratio. So, Cost analysis, commonly referred to as cost-benefit analysis which is the process of estimating prospective profits from a scenario and deducting any associated costs.

Benefit cost ratio is affected by different parameters like fixed cost, Variable cost, selling price of produce and yield. All these parameters will affect the cost price and selling price, ultimately affecting the profit.

Fixed cost which is not change during the entire season it include cost of the land and maintenance cost. In the present experiment cost of land for all the treatment combination was (47.14 Rs./m²) with maintenance cost of (23.57 Rs./m²). Fixed cost is sum of cost of land and maintenance cost. In this experiment fixed cost is 70.71 Rs./m² for every combination.

Variable cost varies with the market conditions, it includes cost of the seed. The cost of different hybrid seed varies such as cost of Heem Sohna (5.88 Rs./m²), Abhinav (10 Rs./m²) and TO-1057 (13.1 Rs./m²). In this experiment cost of fertilizers, cost of labour, cost of staking, cost of plant protection was fixed for all treatment combination 11.24 Rs./m², 120 Rs./m², 2 Rs./m², 6 Rs./m² respectively. The cost of cultivation across all planting dates was the same, but the cost of cultivation of hybrids was higher and minimum due to rate of hybrids. So, the result revealed that, the cost of cultivation was higher (223.05 Rs./m²) in hybrid H₃(TO-1057), whereas the minimum cost of cultivation (145.12 Rs./m²) was recorded in hybrid H₁ (Heem Shona). This could be due to the higher rate of hybrid seed (TO-1057), that's why the cost of cultivation was maximum in this particular hybrid whereas the lost cost of seed of

Heem Shona was lower as compare to other seed of hybrid, so that the cost of cultivation of Heem Shona was minimum.

The maximum gross return was higher (418.69 Rs.m⁻²) in interaction H₃D₂ (TO-1057 which was transplanted on 15th April 2022). This could be due to higher average yield (6.44 kgm⁻²) in combination of H₃D₂. The minimum gross return (259 Rs.m⁻²) was recorded in interaction H₁D₃ (Heem Sohna which was transplanted on 30th April 2022), due to low yield (3.99 kg m⁻²).

Table 1. Benefit Cost Ratio

Treatment	Total cost price			Total selling price of fruits				
	Fixed cost (Rs.)	Variable cost (Rs.)	Total Cost (Rs.)	Yield (Kg)	Rate/Kg (Rs.)	Gross Return (Rs.)	Net Return (Rs.)	B:C
H ₁ D ₁	70.71	145.12	215.83	4.93	65	320.60	104.77	0.49
H ₂ D ₁	70.71	149.24	219.95	4.87	65	316.83	96.88	0.44
H ₃ D ₁	70.71	152.34	223.05	6.06	65	393.81	170.76	0.77
H ₁ D ₂	70.71	145.12	215.83	5.15	65	334.73	118.90	0.55
H ₂ D ₂	70.71	149.24	219.95	6.33	65	411.36	191.41	0.87
H ₃ D ₂	70.71	152.34	223.05	6.44	65	418.69	195.64	0.88
H ₁ D ₃	70.71	145.12	215.83	3.99	65	259.30	43.47	0.20
H ₂ D ₃	70.71	149.24	219.95	5.04	65	327.30	107.35	0.49
H ₃ D ₃	70.71	152.34	223.05	5.67	65	368.57	145.52	0.65
Total	636.39	1340.1	1976.49	48.48	585	3125.85	1149.36	5.21

*D₁=Transplanting on 30th March 2022, D₂=Transplanting on 15th April 2022, D₃=30th April 2022, H₁=Heem Sohna, H₂=Abhinav, H₃=TO-1057, SE (d)=Standard Deviation, CD=Critical Difference.

However, 15th April 2022 planted date of crop, production of tomato was beneficial from a commercial perspective since it allows for quick access, rising demands, and higher market rates. When compared to planting dates, the early planted date with unfavourable climatic circumstances was not increase tomato fruit yield or quality. (This similar result finding with accordance of Sahoo B B et al. 2021). Hence, this date of transplanted crop with hybrid TO-1057 recommended for commercial tomato production in polyhouse condition.

References

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When conducting a cost-benefit analysis to assess the viability of cash flows produced by an asset, the benefit cost ratio is a profitability indicator that is used. Divide the benefit by the overall cost price to get the cost of the benefit. Among the different treatment combination H₃D₂ (TO-1057 was transplanted on 15th April 2022) recorded highest net return of Rs. 195.64/m² and gives benefit cost ratio is 0.88/m². The perusal of data regarding benefit cost ratio in Table 1.

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